

CHILDREN WITH DEVIANT BEHAVIOR

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Annotation: This article provides support for the mental states of children with deviant behavior through pedagogical methods and methods, as well as specific causes of deviant behavior, and the issue of pedagogical and mental prevention.

Key words: behavior, deviant behavior, addiction, family, crime, bureaucracy, prevention, children with deviant behavior.

INTRODUCTION

In society, the activities, actions and behaviors of people are governed by social norms. Social norms are an integral part of society management, and social behavior is a set of rules that adjust the behavior of an individual or a group to a specific social environment. The problems of the sociology of deviant behavior, which studies cases of deviation from the social norms established in society, in Uzbekistan began to be studied with the honor of independence. It is known that there is no single approach to the theory of deviant behavior. Along with various sociological, pedagogical, psychological and other approaches, the biological approach is also improving. Deviant behavior is especially characteristic of minors. During this period, the personal characteristics of minors are formed. The child's view of the world is embodied in personal thoughts. However, the formation and development of the personality is a complex process and creates unique difficulties. Children with deviant behavior (deviant behavior) every what actions they perform without thinking about the end. They cannot control themselves. There are many such people in society.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The following are some of the more common forms of deviant behavior:

1. Crime;
2. Drunkenness;
3. Drug addiction;
4. Prostitution;

such types serve to pollute the life of the society.

Crime. The negative attitude of some people towards the laws and norms established in a certain country is a criminal activity. The person who has done such things is considered a criminal. At the heart of this is human interest, also at risk.

Alcoholism (lot alcoholismus), that is, drunkenness, also causes many problems in the life of society. In this case, a person suffers from a chronic mental progressive disease, that is, it is characterized by addiction to alcohol and mental and physical dependence on it.

Addiction. drug addiction, drug addiction - a disease state caused by temporary or chronic consumption of natural or synthetic toxic substances (certain drugs).

Prostitution is sex for money or other benefits. Adultery occurs mainly among women and is divided into two types:

1. Cohabitation - living together without marriage.
2. Prostitution - selling one's body for money.

Although the problem of deviant behavior was first specifically studied by E. Durkheim within the scope of sociology, this problem has been formed since ancient times. E. Durkheim explains the law, non-recognition of laws and non-compliance with the term "Anomania" which he introduced to the science.

In a more in-depth analysis of the problem of social norms and deviation from them: Mantesque, Rousseau, Beccorio, Gelvetsey, Diderot, Holbax, Morelli

and Fourier are incomparable. It is possible to indicate 3 factors that are important in the emergence and formation and development of deviant situations in individuals:

1. Personal characteristics;
2. Problem situations;
3. Institutions of social control;

It is these factors that determine a person's place in society and how they function. The occurrence of social deviations depends on a person's determination or lack of determination, habits of obeying or disobeying rules, how much he is given to external influences, his will and other factors. such psychophysiological conditions also have a great effect. In adolescence, there is a constant increase in the manifestation of deviance. At this age, regardless of whether a teenager is a girl or a boy, they are very impressionable, some of them become very introverted. This is a period of certain difficulties. In the family, the environment first of all affects the teenager. For parents, this period is also full of trials. In addition, the pedagogue and psychologists working in the educational institution have a heavy burden. In this, it is appropriate for the pedagogue-psychologist to use various methods and methods to demonstrate the condition of the teenager. One technology is their rehabilitation. Rehabilitation can be considered as a system of measures aimed at solving issues ranging from a wide range of tasks and simple skills to full integration of a person into society. Rehabilitation facilities include:

These are:

1. Socially and pedagogically neglected children.
2. Juvenile offenders, orphans, teenagers with deviant behavior.

Currently, orphanhood in society can be distinguished by two concepts:

1. Orphan (absence of no one), social orphan (lack of role of parents or relatives in the life of society).

2. Children with impaired psychosomatic and neuro-psychological health and functional deviations:

- nervous - mental illnesses;
- chronic somatic diseases;
- mental retardation;
- disability;
- functional disorders.

Children of this category are primarily in need of medical and mental rehabilitation. Their subjects are doctors and psychologists. They can work together and solve the problem from all sides. In addition, calling pedagogues for help and producing complex programs will meet the goal. When creating rehabilitation programs for working with adolescents with deviant behavior, the following are taken into account:

1. Relying on and taking into account the positive aspects of a minor. A social pedagogue has no right to condemn a child with deviant behavior or reveal his faults to his face. He should only look for his good feelings.

2. Formation of life aspirations in a child with deviant behavior. Usually, after chronic failures in school or in life, teenagers feel hopeless. They lose self-confidence. After this situation, the adolescent's desire for professional self-realization weakens. The attention of the social pedagogue is focused on understanding his future profession. Of course, with the help of a psychologist.

3. Involvement in social activities important for children with deviant behavior is one of the complex tasks. Because it is very difficult to involve such a child in any activity. It is natural for them to resist any work at first. such an action requires great effort from a pedagogue or psychologist.

4. Treating relationships with teenagers with respect. Due to the lack of good behavior in maladaptive children, any educational influence is strongly resisted by the minor. Working with such a child requires patience from the social

pedagogue.

The pedagogue develops skills and adaptability in a child with deviant behavior through an all-round approach. Through this way, positive characteristics begin to form in the teenager. The social pedagogue should work not only with the teenager, but also with his family. Family environment, the relationship of family members to each other are the factors that have the strongest influence on a teenager. Deviant behavior is more often observed in adolescents without a father or mother. Such children are orphans. They have less love for life than children with parents. Because the worries of life and not being able to see a loved one creates the basis for the formation of deviant behavior. In order for the teenager not to fall into such a path, various preventive measures should be carried out in the school. Social and pedagogical rehabilitation centers are responsible for preventing such situations.

CONCLUSION

Social pedagogical rehabilitation in educational institutions is aimed at preventing family and school repressions against neglected children and adolescents with various changes in their character, solving conflict situations and problems, as well as restoring them as subjects of educational activities.

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